

Development of Memory Efficient Sampling Methods for Elastic Scattering Angular Distributions

Charlotte Wickert^{1,*}, Benoit Forget¹

¹Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803395

ABSTRACT

Accurate modeling of neutron scattering angular distributions is critical for reliable simulations of leaky systems such as microreactors, space reactors, or fusion devices. However, in many standard nuclear data libraries, detailed features of these distributions are averaged or smoothed out to reduce file size and simplify processing. This work presents two new Monte Carlo sampling techniques that directly use Legendre coefficients derived from Blatt–Biedenharn Formalism to preserve the resonance physics of elastic scattering. These new approaches eliminate the need for precomputed tabulated angular distributions, substantially reducing memory overhead while maintaining physical fidelity. Testing and validation are performed with OpenMC where the new methods reproduce standard table-lookup results within 0.16% accuracy while reducing angular data storage requirements by nearly an order of magnitude. The framework is further extended to include Doppler broadening of Legendre coefficients, enabling temperature-dependent scattering consistent with the underlying resonance structure. These techniques establish a foundation for more physically consistent and memory-efficient transport simulations for shielding applications.

Keywords: OpenMC, Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism, Doppler Broadening, Angular Distributions

1. INTRODUCTION

Although current nuclear reactor modeling techniques provide high accuracy, truly predictive simulations require improved nuclear data and associated computational models. While most materials and models preserve integral quantities well for well-characterized reactor designs, advanced reactors and novel applications can strain the limits of current nuclear data evaluations. Accurately representing scattering angular distributions is particularly important for simulating leaky systems, which are more sensitive to the neutron reflection and transmission ratios.

Despite their importance, nuances of the scattering angular distribution have been largely overlooked in nuclear data. In the resolved resonance region, the angle-integrated scattering cross section is often derived from experimental transmission and capture cross sections [1], whereas the angular distribution is calculated separately using different codes and underlying models. This decoupling results in inconsistencies between the angle-integrated cross sections and their corresponding scattering angular distributions [2].

Across multiple integral experiments, reactivity changes of 100–200 pcm have been attributed to inconsistencies in angular distribution modeling [3]. Similarly, Monte Carlo models of the ICSBEP HEU-MET-FAST-001 (GODIVA) assembly showed significant variation in the reflector thickness needed to maintain criticality when comparing different nuclear data libraries and the angular distribution models [4]. Recent work from the authors found relative differences of up to 20% in the transmission and reflection coefficients for monoenergetic neutrons incident on a slab of material[5].

*cwickert@mit.edu

These inconsistencies reveal the underlying scattering physics of the system may be misrepresented, potentially leading to compensating errors in other model parameters and reduced confidence in simulation results. This work aims to improve the physical treatment of angular distributions by generating and directly sampling Legendre coefficients derived from Blatt–Biedenharn Formalism. Two new OpenMC sampling routines, rejection sampling and “modified moment” sampling, are developed to enable implementation of this physically consistent representation without large memory overhead.

1.1. Evaluated Nuclear Data

Evaluated nuclear data combine experimental measurements and theoretical models to estimate physical parameters essential for nuclear simulations such as cross sections and angular distributions [2]. This data is organized and distributed in standardized formats, most commonly the ENDF-6 format.

In ENDF-6, scattering angular distributions are represented as normalized probability distributions,

$$\int_{-1}^1 f(\mu, E) d\mu = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $f(\mu, E)d\mu$ is the probability of a neutron of incident energy E scattering into the interval $d\mu$ about the scattering angle $\mu = \cos(\theta)$. Angular distributions are stored in one of four representations:

1. Isotropic distributions (equal probability for all angles)
2. Legendre polynomial expansion with energy-dependent coefficients $a_L(E)$
3. Tabulated probability distributions $f(\mu, E)$
4. Hybrid data with Legendre coefficients at low energies and tabulated data at high energies

The Legendre polynomial representation is most relevant to this work as the coefficients can be directly related to the resonance parameters in ENDF File 2 through Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism. The expansion is expressed as

$$f(\mu, E) = \sum_{L=0}^{N_L} \frac{2L+1}{2} a_L(E) P_L(\mu) \quad (2)$$

where $P_L(\mu)$ is the L^{th} Legendre polynomial, $a_L(E)$ is the corresponding moment, N_L the maximum order, and $\frac{2L+1}{2}$ is the normalization factor. In modern evaluations, such as ENDF/B VIII.1 [6], these moments are often smooth functions of energy (Figure 1a); however, physically, they should exhibit resonance structure consistent with the Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism due to the anisotropy of in-resonance scattering (Figure 1b).

Not all isotopes in ENDF/B VIII.1 have resonance parameters suitable for generating Legendre coefficients. When all resonance spins and parities are known, Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism derived angular distributions should be exact and physically consistent. However, incomplete resonance information can produce inaccurate results limiting the Formalism’s applicability [2]. As a result, most ENDF angular distributions are based on sparse experimental data or optical model calculations, both of which are approximations of the underlying resonant structure. Evaluators indicate whether the resonance parameters are suitable for generating Legendre moments.

1.2. Limitations

In the ENDF format, angular distributions are stored as expansions of Legendre moments. However, standard Monte Carlo transport methods require tabulated probability and cumulative distribution functions (PDF and CDFs) constructed from these coefficients. For each incident energy, the PDF and CDF must be represented as histograms over the cosine of the scattering angle. When the resonance structure introduced by the Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism is fully resolved, the number of angular data

(a) The Cu63 ENDF/B VIII.1 Legendre moments are a smooth function of energy, where resonance effects have been averaged out.

(b) The Cu63 Legendre moments generated from Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism have resonance structure.

Figure 1. Comparison of Cu63 Legendre moments between ENDF/B VIII.1 and Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism.

points increases $6 - 9 \times$ compared to the smoothed ENDF/B VIII.1 evaluations[5], significantly increasing memory requirements.

The introduction of resonance structure in the Legendre moments also requires accounting for Doppler broadening, which further increases the data storage requirement to represent tabulated temperature-dependent data. These challenges motivate the development of more efficient methods that operate directly on the physical Legendre coefficients without the need for precomputed tabular data. The next section presents two Monte Carlo sampling techniques, rejection sampling and “modified moment” sampling, that preserve the resonance-resolved physics of Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism while reducing data storage.

2. COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

2.1. Current Methods

In standard Monte Carlo transport simulations, the scattering angle for elastic collisions is sampled from tabular angular distributions or isotropically in the absence of tabulated data. The outgoing energy is then determined analytically from kinematics.

For each stored incident neutron energy, the angular data are represented by a discrete set of cosine values, PDF probabilities, and cumulative values for the CDF.

2.2. Direct Legendre Sampling Methods

Table-lookup sampling schemes, while computationally efficient, require large amounts of memory. For angular distribution data, increasing the number of energy bins significantly increases memory requirements. However, eliminating the need to generate tabular distributions can mitigate this memory increase. Rejection sampling can be used for arbitrary Legendre order, while the modified moment method, in its current form, only applies to special cases of second-order moments. Of the 47 isotopes in ENDF/B VIII.1 for which Blatt-Biedenharn coefficients may be generated, 29 of them only have second-order moments in the resonance region. For the remainder of this work, one of these 29 isotopes, Cu63, will be used as a test case.

In the Cu63 resolved resonance region, where Blatt-Biedenharn coefficients have been generated, there are two stored coefficients a_1 and a_2 for each energy E . The zeroth moment a_0 is always equal to 1. The PDF $f(\mu, E)$ is calculated with equation 2 using the first three Legendre polynomials. For example, at 48.24616 keV, Cu63 has the following coefficients: $a_0 = 1; a_1 = 0.2631709; a_2 = -0.01860764$.

Traditionally, when Legendre moments are used for multigroup cross sections, sampling is complicated by the negative values in probability distribution functions (PDFs). However, for the continuous energy data in ENDF/B VIII.1, the coefficients are normalized so that the combined PDF is positive for all μ -values, enabling rejection sampling and sampling from modified versions of the Legendre basis set. Both of these methods will be discussed below.

2.2.1. Rejection Sampling

Rejection sampling is a standard scheme to sample from a known PDF when the CDF inversion is intractable. This method requires the maximum of the function to be known. For functions composed of two orders of Legendre polynomials, the maximum value must occur at one of the maxima or minima of the basis functions as the weights act as scaling factors. For the first two Legendre orders, the maximum of the composite PDF must occur at one of $[-1, 0, 1]$.

2.2.2. Modified Moment Sampling

For special cases of second-order representations, the terms of the basis functions may be rearranged to force the polynomials to always be positive and to allow for direct inversion sampling. Using the example values introduced above, the zeroth moment $\frac{1}{2}P_0 = \frac{1}{2}$ may be distributed between the high order moments to go from the original basis functions $P_1(x), P_2(x)$ to the modified moments $q_1(x), q_2(x)$ with CDFs $Q_1(x), Q_2(x)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3}{2}a_1P_1(x) &= \frac{3}{2}a_1x \rightarrow \\ q_1(x) &= \frac{3}{2}(a_1x + |a_1|) \\ \\ \frac{5}{2}a_2P_2(x) &= \frac{5}{4}a_2(3x^2 - 1) \rightarrow \\ q_2(x) &= \frac{5}{4}a_2(3x^2 - 1) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3|a_1|) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2. Modified moment basis functions $q_1(x)$ and $q_2(x)$ form the composite PDF.

Integrating each of these new moment functions over the domain $[-1, 1]$ gives the fraction of the total probability each contains.

$$w_1 = \int_{-1}^1 q_1(x)dx = 3|a_1| \quad (3)$$

$$w_2 = \int_{-1}^1 q_2(x)dx = 1 - 3|a_1| \quad (4)$$

Each time the scattering angle is sampled, the routine will pick which modified moment to sample based on these integration factors. The CDFs of these modified moments are invertible offering an alternative for sharp functions tricky to sample using rejection sampling. This method is valid for second-order

$$Q_1(x) = \int_{-1}^x q_1(x') dx' = \frac{3}{4} (a_1 x^2 + 2|a_1|x - a_1 + 2|a_1|)$$

$$Q_2(x) = \int_{-1}^x q_2(x') dx' = \frac{5}{4} a_2 x^3 - \frac{1}{4} (5a_2 - 2 + 6|a_1|) x + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2} |a_1|$$

Figure 3. Integrated modified moment functions $Q_1(x)$ and $Q_2(x)$ form the composite CDF.

expansions where $|a_1| < \frac{1}{3}$ and $a_2 < \frac{2(1-3|a_1|)}{5}$ otherwise, standard rejection sampling is used. For coefficients that do not meet these criteria, splitting the zeroth order moment alone is not enough to make the new basis functions positive for all x-values. The logic for the sampling scheme is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Modified Moment Sampling

```

if  $|a_1| < \frac{1}{3}$  and  $a_2 < \frac{2(1-3|a_1|)}{5}$  then                                ▷ Check that coefficients satisfy positivity constraints
  Generate  $\xi_1, \xi_2 \sim U[0, 1]$ 
  Compute  $w_1 = 3|a_1|, w_2 = 1 - w_1$ 
  if  $\xi_1 < w_1$  then
     $\mu \leftarrow Q_1^{-1}(\xi_2 \times w_1)$                                        ▷ Sample from 1st-order modified moment
  else
     $\mu \leftarrow Q_2^{-1}(\xi_2 \times w_2)$                                        ▷ Sample from 2nd-order modified moment
  end if
  return  $\mu$ 
else
  Rejection sample                                                         ▷ Fallback if positivity violated
end if

```

2.3. Doppler Broadening

The resonance structure introduced by Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism requires new methods for handling temperature effects. To incorporate these temperature effects into Blatt-Biedenharn distributions, the Leal-Hwang Doppler[7] broadening method was extended to operate on Legendre coefficients rather than total cross sections as previously suggested by V. Sobes[1].

The Doppler broadened cross section $\sigma(E, T)$ discretized as a function of energy E and temperature T can be related to the cross section at any lower temperature T_0 by

$$\sigma(E, T) = 1/E \sum_{k=-j}^j a_k^j E_k \sigma(E_k, T_0) \tag{5}$$

where a_k^j are weighting coefficients, E_k are discrete energy points with temperature dependent energy

spacing.

Applying the same methodology to the Legendre coefficients gives the following temperature dependent function (Figure 4) which provides a method of calculating the temperature dependent Legendre coefficients based on the total cross section and Legendre coefficients at 0K.

$$\alpha_l(E, T) = \frac{\sum_{k=-j}^j a_k^j E_k \sigma(E_k, T_0) \alpha_l(E_k, T_0)}{\sum_{k=-j}^j a_k^j E_k \sigma(E_k, T_0)}$$

Figure 4. The Leal-Hwang Doppler broadening methodology applied to Blatt-Biedenharn Legendre coefficients produces similar behavior to total cross sections, the ENDF coefficients remain unchanged.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Results from a thin-slab model are presented to validate the proposed sampling methods and quantify their computational advantages for a 0K and 600K case. Transmission, reflection, and memory requirements are compared across models.

3.1. Thin Slab Model

Neutron transmission and reflection fractions were tallied for a monoenergetic neutron beam incident on a thin slab of Cu63 with a width of five mean free paths. The neutron beam energy was set to 48.24616 keV which corresponds to a Cu63 resonance where the ENDF and Blatt-Biedenharn data differ (Figure 4). For the ENDF and Blatt-Biedenharn table-lookup cases, NJOY was used to generate ACE files from ENDF tapes for use in OpenMC. For the new methods, the Legendre coefficients were read in directly. In the resonance region, when OpenMC performs angular sampling for elastic collisions, the new methods were called instead.

3.2. Results

Transmission and reflection fractions for the various cases and their absolute relative difference compared to the Blatt-Biedenharn Table-Lookup case are shown in Table I. The final column shows the number of points required to represent the data used in each model. The ENDF/B VIII.1 and B-B Table-Lookup models require cosine, PDF, and CDF values while the rejection and modified moment sampling schemes only need the Legendre coefficients at each energy. The rejection sampling method is able to correctly reproduce the table results within error margins. The modified moment sampling method represents an improved treatment of the data when compared to the original ENDF/B VIII.1 data.

The 600K case highlights the importance of incorporating angular resonance temperature effects. The Doppler broadening method described in the previous section was applied to the ENDF and Blatt-

Model	Transmission		Reflection		Points
	Value	Abs. Rel. Diff. (%)	Value	Abs. Rel. Diff. (%)	
B-B Table-Lookup	0.10112(7)	-	0.28683(10)	-	296,649
ENDF Table-Lookup	0.08874(6)	13.95(11)	0.30047(10)	4.54(5)	15,519
B-B Rejection	0.10108(7)	0.04(9)	0.28682(10)	0.00(5)	33,436
B-B Modified Moment	0.10096 (7)	0.16(9)	0.28693(10)	0.03(5)	33,436

Table I. Rejection and modified moment sampling reproduce the Blatt-Biedenharn table-lookup results within < 0.16% while reducing memory usage by an order of magnitude.

Model	Transmission		Reflection	
	Value	Abs. Rel. Diff. (%)	Value	Abs. Rel. Diff. (%)
B-B Table-Lookup 600K	0.09494(7)	-	0.29366(10)	-
B-B Table-Lookup 0K	0.10112(7)	6.12(9)	0.28683(10)	2.38(5)
ENDF Table-Lookup 0K	0.08874(6)	6.98(11)	0.30047(10)	2.27(5)
ENDF Table-Lookup 600K	0.08874(6)	6.53(10)	0.30047(10)	2.32(5)
B-B Rejection 600K	0.09485(7)	0.09(10)	0.29374(10)	0.03(5)
B-B Modified Moment 600K	0.09478(6)	0.16(10)	0.29377(11)	0.04(5)

Table II. Relative differences in transmission and reflection including temperature effects.

Biedenharn data. The Legendre coefficients in the ENDF case are smooth functions of energy and are unaffected by the Doppler broadening methods. In contrast, in the Blatt-Biedenharn case, Doppler broadening reduces the magnitude of the resonances, decreasing the effect on transport as visualized in Figure 4 when compared to the 0K case. This is also observed in the lower absolute relative difference when comparing the ENDF and Blatt-Biedenharn implementations as shown in Table II.

Using unbroadened (0K) Blatt-Biedenharn data in a 600K OpenMC simulation, however, produces a level of deviation comparable to neglecting resonance effects altogether. Therefore, Blatt-Biedenharn generated angular distributions cannot be utilized accurately without properly accounting for temperature effects. Although several isotopes in recent releases of ENDF have Legendre coefficients derived from Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism, the data are provided at 0K. Without appropriate Doppler broadening, users risk introducing biases that may wrongly be compensated by adjustments in other parts of the nuclear data.

Even with the current prototype implementation, the rejection sampling approach outperforms the standard Blatt-Biedenharn table-lookup scheme in OpenMC as shown in Table III.

Model	Time in Simulation (seconds)
B-B Table-Lookup	24.026
ENDF Table-Lookup	17.278
B-B Rejection	19.340
B-B Modified Moment	25.970

Table III. Rejection sampling is faster than the full Blatt-Biedenharn table-lookup method.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces two direct Legendre coefficient sampling methods for Monte Carlo transport that enable physically consistent, memory-efficient treatment of scattering angular distributions derived

from Blatt–Biedenharn Formalism.

These results demonstrate that direct Legendre coefficient sampling provides a practical approach toward more physically consistent, temperature-dependent transport simulations without increased computation and memory costs. The new methods reproduce table-lookup results within 0.16%, rejection sampling within statistical uncertainty, while reducing memory by nearly an order of magnitude.

Future work will extend these methods to higher-order Legendre coefficients, improve efficiency, and integrate them into benchmark criticality and shielding problems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by a Department of the Air Force Developing the Airmen We Need-Education (DAWN-ED) Fellowship for alternative energy.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Sobes. *Coupled differential and integral data analysis for improved uncertainty quantification of the $^{63,65}\text{Cu}$ cross section evaluations*. Ph.D. thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (2014).
- [2] D. A. Brown. “ENDF-6 Formats Manual - Data Formats and Procedures for the Evaluated Nuclear Data Files ENDF/B-VI, ENDF/B-VII and ENDF/B-VIII.” Technical report, Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL), Upton, NY (United States) (2023). URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/2007538>.
- [3] G. Noguere, C. Jouanne, O. Leray, P. Archier, and C. Vaglio-Gaudard. “Elastic Scattering Angular Distributions In The Fast Energy Range.” Presented at the WPEC Meeting, Issy-les-Moulineaux, France (2013). 22 May 2013.
- [4] V. D. Zhukov, A. S. Listov, V. G. Pronyaev, and V. V. Sinitsa. “Estimation of the influence of elastic neutron scattering anisotropy on the integral parameters of the model experiment.” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 1689(1), p. 012018 (2020). URL <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1689/1/012018>.
- [5] C. Wickert and B. Forget. “Evaluating the Effect of Blatt-Biedenharn Formalism on Neutron Angular Scattering Behavior.” In *Proceedings of the American Nuclear Society Annual Conference 2025*, pp. 1055–1058. American Nuclear Society, Chicago, IL, USA (2025). Reactor Analysis Methods: II.
- [6] G. P. A. Nobre et al. “ENDF/B-VIII.1: Updated Nuclear Reaction Data Library for Science and Applications.” (2025). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.03564>.
- [7] L. C. Leal and R. N. Hwang. “A Finite Difference Method for Treating the Doppler Broadening of Neutron Cross Sections.” In *Transactions of the American Nuclear Society*, volume 55, pp. 340–342 (1987).